

THE INTEGRATION OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH WITH AI TO TEACH THE SECOND LANGUAGE EFFECTIVELY.

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Annotation: *In this article , communicative approach is approved widely by ESL and EFL learners in order to be fluent in their target language . Moreover , modern technologies and AI can be helpful to master English and I will explain how CLT approach can be integrated with them to produce a language. Moreover, the effect of age , culture and realizing students`motivation will be analyzed deeply.*

Key words: *communicative approach, key factors , motivation , AI , fluency .*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada, kommunikativ yondashuv (communicative approach) ESL va EFL o`rganuvchilar tomonidan maqsad tilida ravon gapira olish uchun keng qo`llanilishi tasdiqlanadi. Bundan tashqari, zamonaviy texnologiyalar va sun`iy intellekt (AI) ingliz tilini mukammal o`rganishda yordam berishi mumkinligi va CLT yondashuvi ularni qanday birlashtirib, tilni ishlab chiqarishga (language production) olib kelishi tushuntiriladi. Shuningdek, yosh, madaniyat ta`siri va talabalarning motivatsiyasini anglash masalalari chuqur tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so`zlar: kommunikativ yondashuv, asosiy omillar, motivatsiya, sun`iy intellekt, ravonlik.

Аннотация: *В данной статье коммуникативный подход широко признается учащимися ESL и EFL для достижения беглости в изучаемом языке. Более того, современные технологии и искусственный интеллект (ИИ) могут помочь в освоении английского языка, и я объясню, как подход CLT можно интегрировать с ними для развития речевой продукции. Также будет проведён глубокий анализ влияния возраста, культуры и понимания мотивации студентов.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативный подход, ключевые факторы, мотивация, ИИ, беглость.*

INTRODUCTION:

The role and influence of English today are gaining a higher speed in the world. The main factors for this phenomenon include expanding communication with the

world after gaining independence and increasing speed and scope of information exchange in the global village. The dominant position in the internet space by the language of the published content is firmly held by English, which is a strong motivation to learn English for those who wish to promote their global competencies [Brandl,K].

As the English language is globalizing, different approaches are used by the teachers to help students learn the target language. However, the communicative approach is considered as the most useful tool to master the language. Even though this approach has prevailed over the past 50 years, it is still used nowadays.

The origins of the Communicative Approach are to be found in the late 1960s and early 1970s. The communicative approach is the product of some linguists and educators who had grown dissatisfied with the previous two methods used for foreign language teaching; the audio-lingual method and Grammar-translation method. These great linguists and educators who contributed to the rise of this worldwide used approach are Hymes, Chomsky, Wilkins, Van Ek and Alexander, and the Council of Europe.

However, all these linguists and educators felt that students during those years were not learning the language in the right way. They claimed that they did not learn the 'whole language' and realistic language. Students did not know how to communicate outside the classroom in real life situations, using the appropriate social language. So far they were relying on the structures of language instead of relying on functions and notions of language. This made them unable to communicate in the culture of the language studied [Spada,N 2007].

How does communicative approach help EFL[English as a foreign language] students

This approach is based on the idea that learning a language successfully comes through having daily communication. Therefore, it encourage students to speak even if they do not know grammar rules. As a result, their communicational skill in English can be boosted. Firstly, the teacher act as a role model of good communicator. It includes asking clear questions, providing direct answers and giving clear instructions to the students. Importantly, conversation, class discussion and even grammar lessons should be in English.

The role of AI

In learning language environment, Artificial intelligence offers numerous benefits for fostering communicational skills. AI-powered platforms such as chatbots or speech recognition tools give clear and valid feedback on pronunciation, grammar and fluency. Even AI can adapt to learners' levels, offering personalized exercises and error correction, making communicative approach more student-centered. Moreover,

ChatGPT can act a real partner for realistic dialogues on various topics and it provides unlimited speaking practice , reducing learners` anxiety and helping them gain confidence .

The concept of Artificial intelligence was emerged in 1956 , but modern breakthroughs: IBM`s Watson(Jeopardy champion in 2011), AlphaGo (2016) and ChatGPT (2019) have showcased AI`s increasing capabilities.

There are several benefits of AI for learning a language effectively .

1.Personalized learning: AI algorithms can create adapted learning plans with analyzing a learner`s performance ,preferences and learning style.

2.Interactive practice .AI-driven chatbots (CHatGPT, Siri, Bixby) make learning process more engaging . The reason these platforms are useful for communicative approach is that not all language learners are open to conversation with others. They are concerned about speaking in another language in front of others and these tools create an environment for free communication.

3. Immediate grading.

In traditional language learning methods , students often waste time for waiting for a teacher or being assessed, but with the help of AI, student can receive instant feedback on their grammar, vocabulary , pronunciation and speaking ability which enables them to correct their mistakes.

CHALLENGES IN AI IMPLEMENTATION WITH CLT APPROACH.

1. Equitable access : Even though we are surrounded with modern technologies , not all students have reliable internet or device access and they can not use these chances.
2. Ethical and Privacy concerns: While talking with AI , privacy will be at risk . This is because AI systems collects vast amounts of learner data , raising concerns about privacy, and data ownership.

Conclusion.

In order to know the result , I observed 7th class at 43 rd school during the internship. Before the month they had a main problem with learning English , even if they had phones , they did not use Chat GPT for educational aim. In every lesson, they were motivated to speak with their peers and a teacher only in English. Firstly they struggled ,but after a week, significant progress was seen in their learning a language. They were taught how to use Chat GPT effectively for making conversation , creating daily plans , providing with feedback . In a month , pupils were taught successfully with CLT methodology and AI platform. Not only did they learn the language , but also they improved their self-esteem , tech-knowledge and future goal with exchanging ideas , speaking in English and using AI.

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